

Synthesis of Some Fluorodiphenylamines and Fluorophenothiazines and IR Studies of their Structures

K. C. Joshi and (Mrs.) Jharna Sen Gupta

Starting from substituted acetanilides and fluorobromobenzenes, several new fluorodiphenylamines have been prepared. These have been characterised through their benzoyl derivatives. The attempted conversion of these fluorodiphenylamines into fluorophenothiazines has been described. The IR spectra of some of these fluorophenothiazines have been studied for their structure determination.⁵

The phenothiazine nucleus possesses interesting biological properties; important psychotropic drugs like Chlorpromazine are well known¹. Recently, the chemistry of fluorinated phenothiazines has been studied² and some of these compounds have found possible use as antioxidants in lubricating oils used in turbo-jet engines. Most of these compounds are trifluoromethylated phenothiazines. In this communication are reported the syntheses of fluorinated diphenylamines, which themselves may also exhibit important biological properties, and their conversion into fluorinated phenothiazines.

The fluorinated diphenylamines were obtained by the Goldberg condensation of a substituted acetanilide with an aryl halide³. Practically no information is available in the literature regarding the biological properties of such fluorodiphenylamines. These were converted into the corresponding thiazine structure by an iodine-catalysed modification of Bernthsen's fusion⁴ with sulphur. In case of fluorinated diphenylamines, the thionation and cyclisation often do not proceed smoothly and earlier workers⁵ have also reported certain difficulties. In our work, the percentage yield was very low in each case. In some cases, during the thionation reaction, hydrogen sulphide gas was evolved as usual but the final products were either intractable tars or unchanged fluorodiphenylamines. Besides, there is also a possibility of the loss of fluorine during thionation. Of the twelve fluorodiphenylamines, subjected to this reaction, we could achieve some degree of success only in five cases.

Under these circumstances, the structures of the phenothiazines obtained have to be confirmed by other methods. Determination of the structure of a phenothiazine by degradation is difficult; the methods used are to form a diphenylamine by removal of sulphur, or to convert the molecule to a carbazole, or to an acridine⁵. Because of these difficulties, infrared spectroscopy has been applied for structure determination⁵.

1. Burger, "Medicinal Chemistry".
2. Smith, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 1126.
3. *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 4841.
4. *Annalen*, 1855, 230, 182.
5. Roe and Little, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 1877.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

The spectra of four of these compounds are discussed here. As the phenothiazine structure is composed of two benzene rings joined in the *ortho* position, it is expected that each ring should exhibit IR absorption characteristic of the particular substitution present in that ring. Earlier workers^{2,3} have, however, cautioned that in addition to the predicted IR absorption peaks for each compound, additional peaks are found in many cases. The four spectra obtained here have been compared with a standard spectrum of phenothiazine (V). Of the various peaks, phenothiazine(V) has two peaks at 13.3 and 13.6 μ , indicating the region for *o*-disubstitution (for the *ortho* nitrogen and sulphur bridges), and a sharp peak at 3 μ for -NH-. Compound(I) has a spectrum broadly following the phenothiazine pattern with a sharp peak at 3 μ and indicates that thionation has been effected. It has, however, two additional 3.4 and 3.8 micron bands. This could be due to bonded NH. Compound(II) exhibits a spectrum which though following a phenothiazine pattern does not look too good. The -NH- peak at 3 μ is not very sharp. The spectrum does not show sharp bands as in simple phenothiazine(V) and may therefore be impure. The compound, however, provides sufficiently correct analytical data and colour reactions. Compounds(III) and (IV) do not respond to the colour reactions of fluorophenothiazines. The spectra are too broad with no clear -NH- peak at 3 μ and do not have all the peaks of the phenothiazine. In compound (IV) there are, instead, two strong bands at 3.4 and 3.8 μ . During thionation hydrogen sulphide was, however, evolved. On the basis of the existing data, it is difficult to outline the course the reaction taken in these two cases.

FIG. 5

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluorobenzene was obtained from aniline by following the method of Balz and Schiemann⁶.

p-Fluorobromobenzene.—Fluorobenzene (45 g.) was treated with bromine (95.2 g.) in presence of iron filings as catalyst⁷. The fraction boiling at 153-61° was collected as *p*-fluorobromobenzene (yield 40g.) and a second fraction boiling up to 215° was collected and identified as 2,4-dibromofluorobenzene (yield 16 g.). Both the fractions were used for subsequent treatment.

m-Chlorobromobenzene was prepared by following the method of Horning⁸.

6. Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, p. 193.

7. Suter and Weston, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 602.

8. Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, p. 208.

p-Fluoroacetanilide.—*p*-Fluoroaniline, obtained from *p*-fluoronitrobenzene⁹, on acetylation by the usual procedure led to the formation of *p*-fluoroacetanilide, m.p. 150°.

Fluorodiphenylamines.—A reaction mixture of appropriate substituted acetanilide (0.1*M*) and mono- or di-bromofluorobenzene (0.2*M*) was refluxed in nitrobenzene (20-30 ml) under vigorous stirring together with anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.1*M*) and 6.0 g. of a catalyst mixture (consisting of equal parts by weight of cuprous iodide, potassium iodide and copper powder⁹). A crystal of iodine was also added before the reaction started. After refluxing for 17-20 hr. the nitrobenzene solvent and excess bromofluorobenzene were removed by steam-distillation. The solid acetylated fluorodiphenylamine, which remained in the flask, was separated from the reaction mixture by extracting several times with ether. This was dried, the ether removed, and then hydrolysed by 20% EtOH-KOH solution (100 ml). The hydrolysed mixture was poured on saturated salt solution, extracted with ether, dried, and the ether removed. The crude fluorodiphenylamine was distilled under reduced pressure. In each case, the compound was characterised by its benzoyl derivative, prepared in benzene medium. The compounds synthesised are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R.	R'.	B.P.	Benzoyl derivative.		
				M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
1	4'-Br.	4-F	170°/1-1.5 mm	135°	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ONBrF	3.55 3.78
2	4'-Cl.	4-F	249°/0.6	116°	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ONClF	4.00 4.30
3	4'-Cl.	3-Br, 4-F	162°/0.7	120°	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ ONBrClF	3.28 3.46
4	4'-OMe	4-F	104°/1-1.5	86°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ NF	4.20 4.36
5	4'-Br.	3-Br, 4-F	118°/1	110°	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ ONBr ₂ F	2.01 3.11
6	2'-Cl.	4-F	128°/1.5-2	118°	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ONClF	4.02 4.30
7	4'-NO ₂ .	4-F	203°/1.5-2	102°	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ F	8.11 8.33
8	2'-NO ₂ .	4-F	100°/1	120°	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ F	8.00 8.33
9	2'-OMe.	4-F	143°/1	113°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₂ NF	4.12 4.36
10	2'-OMe.	3-Br, 4-F	151°/1.5	123°	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ O ₂ NBrF	3.26 3.50
11	2'-Cl.	3-Br, 4-F	162°/2	116°	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ ONBrClF	3.20 3.46
12	4'-F.	3-Cl	170-71°/1.5	121°	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ ONClF	4.10 4.30

Fluorophenothiazines.—An appropriate fluorodiphenylamine (0.08 *M*) was heated at 200-210° for 3-4 hr. in presence of sulphur (0.16 *M*) and a few crystals of iodine. The resulting tar was boiled with 20% aqueous sodium sulphide to remove unchanged sulphur and then extracted several times with ether. The ethereal layer was dried and distilled

9. Adams, "Organic Reactions", Vol. V, p. 203

under reduced pressure. The products obtained were subjected to colour tests with HNO_3 (conc.) or H_2SO_4 (conc.). Of the compounds synthesised, only two responded to these colour tests and the colour remained unchanged on further dilution.

2-Chloro-7-fluorophenothiazine (I).—2-Chloro-4'-fluorodiphenylamine (12 g.) yielded on usual treatment 2 g. of the desired phenothiazine, recrystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 153°. (Found: N, 5.39. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{NClFS}$ requires N, 5.56%). It developed a red colour with HNO_3 (conc.).

3-Fluoro-7-methoxyphenothiazine (II).—Starting from 4'-fluoro-4-methoxydiphenylamine (19 g.), sulphur (4 g.), and iodine (0.2 g.), the title phenothiazine was obtained; m.p. 75°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 0.20. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{ONFS}$ requires N, 0.65%). It developed a dark red colour with HNO_3 (conc.).

Attempted Synthesis of 3-Fluoro-4-bromo-7-chlorophenothiazine or 3-Fluoro-2-bromo-7-chlorophenothiazine (III).—3-Bromo-4'-chloro-4'-fluorodiphenylamine (10 g.) on similar treatment yielded the fluorophenothiazine (2 g.), m.p. 112°. Cyclisation may result in the formation of either of the above products. The product developed a green colour with HNO_3 (conc.), resembling the behaviour of nonfluorinated phenothiazines⁵. This shows that perhaps in the thionation reaction somehow fluorine had been detached. This possibility is supported by elemental analysis as shown below. The IR data do not correspond to either of these structures. (Found: N, 4.34. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_7\text{NBrClS}$ requires N, 4.48%).

Attempted Synthesis of 3-Fluoro-9-chlorophenothiazine (IV).—By the usual treatment of 2'-chloro-4'-fluorodiphenylamine (10 g.) and sulphur (3 g.) with few crystals of iodine, the fluorophenothiazine was obtained, m.p. 167-70°, yield 1.5 g. It developed a green colour with HNO_3 (conc.). (Found: N, 5.63. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{NClS}$ requires N, 5.99%).

Attempted Synthesis of 3-Fluoro-7-chlorophenothiazine.—4'-Chloro-4'-fluorodiphenylamine (19 g.) on treatment with sulphur yielded the corresponding fluorophenothiazine, b.p. 212°/0.7 mm, yield 5 g. It developed a dark green colour with HNO_3 (conc.). (Found: N, 5.59. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{NClS}$ requires N, 5.99%).

The authors are thankful to Sadtler Research Laboratories, U.S.A., for IR spectra and to Prof. C.N.R. Rao of I.I.T., Kanpur, for some helpful suggestions. One of them (J.S.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship.